

IMPROVING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL
PRODUCTS

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of agricultural products in the economy, their competitiveness in capturing the market, and analyzes the situation and ways of development in Uzbekistan in this context. The competitiveness of products is determined by many factors, which, according to the possibility of influence of the subject of management on the object, are divided into external and internal.*

Keywords. *Products, GDP, economy, competitiveness, market, analyze, agriculture, agricultural products, domestic market, foreign market.*

The reform of the agro-industrial complex led to a sharp decline in the production of agricultural products and food, and a loss of competitiveness of domestic producers in the foreign and domestic markets. For food products sold in retail trade, the share of imports is more than 40%; in large cities and individual industrial centers it reaches 80%. In a market economy, the survival of any enterprise and its stable position in the market for goods and services is determined by the level of competitiveness. Competitive products are products that have higher consumer properties compared to similar products available on the market, and as a result are in increased demand.

Competitiveness can only be determined by comparing the products of competitors with each other. This concept is relative, clearly tied to a specific

market and time of sale (especially for agricultural products). The competitiveness of products is determined by many factors, which, according to the possibility of influence of the subject of management on the object, are divided into external and internal.

External factors include the degree of market competitiveness, price, supply and demand, solvency of the population, standardization and certification, protectionist policies towards domestic producers, natural and climatic conditions, internal factors include product quality, production costs, technology, organization and production management, marketing, product differentiation, innovation, financial condition of the enterprise.

Managing product competitiveness involves targeted influence on internal factors that determine its level, taking into account the influence of the external environment. The competitiveness of products is largely determined by price, which depends on competition in the market. The market for agricultural raw materials and food is characterized by perfect competition and monopolistic competition. The market for agricultural products is characterized by perfect competition. This market includes a large number of independent sellers (agricultural enterprises, farms, private farms) offering standardized goods (wheat, potatoes, sugar beets, etc.), the price of which is determined by the relationship between supply and demand.

Since individual agricultural producers cannot influence prices, they can increase profit margins mainly only by reducing the cost of agricultural products. Monopolistic competition in the agro-industrial complex is typical for the food market. For example, the dairy market, where differentiated products are sold such as animal butter, cheese, cottage cheese, sour cream, yogurt and others, which differ from one another in quality, packaging, trademark, etc.

There are a large number of manufacturers operating in this market who try to convince the buyer that their product is unique in this product group. Product

differentiation allows the dairy product manufacturer to set its own price, regardless of the actions of competitors. But since each manufacturer's sales volume is relatively small, each enterprise has limited control over the market price.

Product competitiveness management is the process of implementing the management function in quality, cost and marketing management systems. Quality management involves establishing, ensuring and maintaining the required level of quality of agricultural products during their production, processing, storage, sale and consumption. Product quality is a set of properties that determine its suitability to satisfy certain needs in accordance with its purpose. The buyer considers quality products to be those that meet the conditions of consumption, regardless of what specific needs they were intended to satisfy. The quality of the same product may be considered high when used for some purposes and low for others. Thus, an increase in the protein content of barley increases its value as fodder, but reduces it as a product for brewing. Quality as an economic category is a social assessment that characterizes the degree of satisfaction of needs in specific conditions of consumption of that set of properties that are clearly expressed or potentially embedded in a product.

The formation and provision of high quality products in the agro-industrial complex have a number of features: product quality must meet the requirements of food safety and health care; the seasonal nature of production in the industry, the dependence of product quality on weather and other natural conditions (droughts, epidemics, invasions of plant pests, etc.).

The dispersion of agricultural production makes it difficult to organize control and operational quality management. In addition, production conditions are related to the socio-demographic and economic situation in the region. Agriculture is characterized by low technical equipment and poor use of information

technology and control methods. The quality of agricultural goods depends both on the production conditions of the product and on its storage and processing.

The transition to the market forces us to take a fresh look at the problem of product quality and competitiveness. The competitiveness of a product is determined only by those properties that are of significant interest to the buyer (for example: size, freshness, taste of the fruit). All other parameters of products (shape, color of fruits) that go beyond these boundaries are not considered when assessing the competitiveness of these products, as they are not related to them in these specific conditions.

A developed competitive market dictates the level and dynamics of product quality development. In this regard, product manufacturers face the challenges of planning and quality management, cost accounting when choosing a more economical option to achieve a certain level. All these problems are successfully solved by introducing a system of quality standards at the enterprise. Quality requirements at the international level are defined by the ISO 9000 series of standards. The standards have penetrated directly into production processes and management, and clear requirements for quality assurance systems have been established. ISO 9000 standards established a unified international approach to contractual terms for assessing quality systems and at the same time regulated the relationship between manufacturers and consumers. Product quality in modern conditions is the most important factor in increasing the profitability of an enterprise's economic activities and, therefore, it needs to be given constant attention. Everyone at the enterprise should be involved in quality – from the manager to the specific performer of any operation.

All processes to ensure and maintain quality are integrated into a quality management system. The quality of agricultural enterprise products is formed with the participation and influence of many factors, primarily production resources

(land, material and labor). There is a great dependence between the quality of agricultural products and the quality of production resources.

Soil is the main environment for the development and nutrition of plants; not only productivity, but also the quality of agricultural products depends on its quality. Practice shows that many types of products grown on fertile soil have increased quality. Thus, potatoes of the highest quality with good keeping quality are obtained on soils that are light in texture (sandy loam). Higher quality characteristics of fixed and material working capital directly contribute to obtaining products of better quality. For example, the use of seeds of high sowing quality allows not only to increase the yield of agricultural crops, but also the quality of the crop; and increasing production and improving the quality of livestock products is greatly influenced by the nutritional quality of feed.

Reliable, high-performance equipment allows you to carry out all agrotechnical practices in a timely manner, in optimal terms and with high quality, and consequently improve the quality of products. The decisive factor in ensuring and constantly improving product quality is improving the quality of labor resources. The qualifications of workers largely determine the quality of work performed. A first class machine operator will perform agricultural work at a higher level than a third class tractor driver. This will ultimately affect the quality of the product.

It should be noted that in the current economic conditions, the quality of work performed largely depends on material incentives. It is necessary to link the level of remuneration to the quality of work and products produced. The quality of agricultural products is determined by the varietal characteristics of cultivated crops and the breed composition of livestock and poultry.

The fertilizer system is one of the most effective factors determining the quality of agricultural products. For each type of plant, optimal doses of mineral fertilizers have been identified to ensure maximum high-quality yield. The

application of fertilizers in higher doses does not increase productivity and reduces the quality of products, while the content of soluble dry substances and sugars in fruits and vegetables decreases, starch in potatoes, and their susceptibility to diseases increases. Irrigation is an important means of regulating the yield and quality of agricultural products. However, excessive watering significantly reduces the commercial quality of products. For each crop, there are optimal timing and irrigation rates; for fruit crops, it is recommended to maintain soil moisture at the level of 65 - 70% of the full field moisture capacity. In many regions of the country it is impossible to grow high-quality vegetable products without irrigation.

The commercial quality of agricultural products depends on many other factors (quality of work performed, timing and methods of harvesting, predecessor, etc.). All this must be taken into account when producing high-quality agricultural products. An important element in the quality management system is certification, which is understood as a set of actions for the purpose of confirming, through a certificate of conformity or mark of conformity, that a product or service complies with certain standards or other regulatory documents. With the help of certification, the final assessment of the quality of manufactured products is carried out.

The objects of mandatory certification include agricultural products. Agricultural enterprises produce a large number of low-quality products.

Every year in Uzbekistan, 10-12% of meat and meat products, 20-24% of canned meat and meat and vegetable products, 18-23% of butter, and 14-16% of vegetable oil of the total volume of inspected goods are rejected and reduced in grade. More than 30% of agricultural products are lost during production, storage, processing and sales.

The main reasons for the low quality of agricultural products are: lack of the necessary material and technical base, untimely implementation of technological operations, insufficient level of professional knowledge of

performers, weak responsibility for the work performed, lack of an effective system of measures of material incentives for workers for achieving high quality indicators. An important role in managing the quality of labor and products should be played by the functional services of an agricultural enterprise (economic, agronomic, veterinary, engineering).

The economic service develops criteria for assessing the quality of labor and products, reasonable standards for production and load of livestock, regulations on material incentives for improving product quality and monitors their implementation.

The Agronomic Service is developing measures to introduce progressive technologies for cultivating agricultural crops, scientifically based crop rotations, effective high-yielding and immune varieties.

The veterinary service develops proposals for improving technological processes in animal husbandry, keeping and caring for livestock, improving breeding work, and observing rations and feeding standards for livestock and poultry.

The engineering service strives to improve the quality of all types of mechanized work, ensures the rational use of equipment and regular technical maintenance, and organizes the replacement of outdated equipment and equipment with new, more productive ones.

Product quality largely depends on the activities of department heads. Their functions include monitoring the implementation of tasks, establishing an objective assessment of the quality of work and products, developing measures aimed at improving quality, and organizing their implementation.

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